

LAST PRESENT: AN OPPORTUNITY FOR PREPARING A GIFT FOR LOVED ONES BEFORE DEATH

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we discuss the relics which people prepare for their loved ones when they face death. Through interviews and cultural probes, we investigated their opinions in regard to these relics and realized their purposes. We also collected the meaningful items in their lives to clarify the relationship between the users and the meaningful objects. During the process of their preparation, we also found some problems and difficulties they encountered. According to the results, we proposed a few design suggestions for designers when they design memorial products or services.

Keywords: Death Memorial Relic

INTRODUCTION

Without exception, death is an event of being separated from loved ones. When facing death, with the urgency of limited time, people are also aware that they will never have another chance to communicate with their love ones. Psychologically, there are several stages people undergo when facing death: after experiencing the feeling of resistance (to the fact) and then truly accepting the inevitability of death, they would review their lives and share their memories with their family in bidding them farewell (Yuko, M. et al., 2006). We assumed that people would try to leave symbolic objects for the sake of remaining within their loved ones' hearts and memories, as well as presenting their hopes of retaining a connection between themselves and their loved ones through the relics.

Traditionally, people left personal items such as rings, watches, clothes or diaries for their family. These intimate items make their family feel honored, serving as a commemoration, and can preserve the identity of the deceased (Hallam, E et al., 2001). As technology advances, some people choose to leave

images, videos, their blogs, or even a digital player embedded in their tombstone. Several related projects offer the potential to combine physical likeness with storage of information, such as a simulation of a human life or an artifact with embedded information (Matthew, L. et al., 2008). The combination of physical artifact and digital content has initiated many new design directions; the final message can be properly preserved for future generations in a family, or for the whole world, in a more interactive way.

The main focus of this project was discussing what people leave behind for their loved ones when facing death, and determining their purposes in leaving such relics behind. From the perspective of those who are leaving, the question was how can they maintain themselves in the hearts of the loved ones and stay connected to those they loved (Dennis K. et al., 1996)? We focused on the relics they select to leave and the form of artifacts they prefer, for our discussion: is it a machine preserving messages and emotions, or a substitute of themselves? What is the meaning of these things in their minds? By studying the items and preferred content, we aimed to figure out the best way for them to leave behind and strengthen their memories among their loved ones.

For the purpose of obtaining a thorough understanding of users, as well as their perspectives, related values and experiences, this project was carried out through two stages. Firstly, in-depth interviews were conducted to understand users' motivations for leaving things behind and their expectations regarding these artifacts. In order to make user to be prepared, respondents were asked to imagine preparing a final relic for their loved ones before the interview. Secondly, we used cultural probe to obtain their preferences and the reasons behind of this object. The findings in this project will

be provided as design suggestions for designers interested in memorial services or products, and promote the new technology opportunities to create interactive memorial services or products.

LITERARY REVIEWS

THE MENTAL PROCESS OF DEATH

When people face death, a complex mental process is involved; death occurs beyond the boundaries of culture and historical moments, social norms and expectations, traditions and innovation (Dennis K. et al., 1996). There are 5 stages when people are dying: at the first four stages, they undergo different kinds of resistance, such as anger, refusal and grief. At the last stage, people go through a process of confirming their reason for being, in relation to the people close to them and take the opportunity to look back upon their own life, and talking about various memories with family members (Yuko, M et al., 2006). In our study, we focus on the last mental stage, helping people to bid farewell with their families or friends.

People build a new connection with their families which are about to be lost; they believed that there is a different space for their loved ones, such as heaven, where they can dream of their families and have dialogues with them. The development of a bond is conscious, dynamic, and changing (Dennis K. et al., 1996). We focused on the perspectives of those who left; the threat of death or separation can initiate a bereavement reaction (Kyriaki, M. et al., 2005). From those who are leaving, we hope to help them ease the pain of their loved ones.

THE MEANING OF THINGS AND ENVIRONMENT

Objects in our live are not simply tools for survival (Csikszentmihalyi, M. 1981); they are also related to people's lives and memories. It is interesting that the emotional attachment appears to be more connected to the functionality of the device, than to the data it contains (Michael, M. et al., 2010). Things differ in the kind of messages they can send about the self (Csikszentmihalyi, M. 1981). In this study, we aimed to help people create a new bond through these objects in their lives.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Due to the sensitivity of this topic, especially in Taiwan, where most people regard death as a taboo and avoid talking about it, we focused on a specific group aged 35-60 who have already purchased before-death contracts, with the obvious assumption that they have already thought of death and are more acceptable to talk about death. There are two parts to the study: In-depth interviews and cultural probes. Through interviews, we could understand their views of these relics and their preferences for existing services. After the interviews, we sent out 10 workbooks to understand their lives and collect the important objects in their lives.

IN-DEPTH INTERVIEWS

The first part of the study was an interview about leaving relics and preparing a last gift for love ones. Before the interview, we defined two kinds of users, "expert", people who have already thought of leaving something for their loved ones and having a plan for the gift; we tried to obtain their opinions and experiences about preparing this gift. The other kind of user is "everyman", people who did not have this situation in their minds before; they did not have a clear vision, but still have some preference about this gift.

Seven people who have already purchased before-death contracts participated, 2 men and 5 women, covering a range of professions (teacher, housewife, customer service, merchant, office worker). Before the interview, we gave participants a few questions about leaving a relic for their love ones in order to make them think about these questions in advance. There were two parts to the interview: their opinions about preparing the relic and their views on existing services. Each session lasted 90-120 min and was recorded.

We started by questioning participants about the most precious things in their lives. We asked what they wanted to prepare for their loved ones and what contents they would use. We also focused on their reasons for leaving such a relic behind. In the second part of the interview, we prepared 8 currently available death-related services for case sharing, including: services which can copy yourself to the virtual world, display your life experience, use

the ashes to make a souvenir, help you to mail letters at a predetermined time before death, help you to record your life into a book and create a personal memorial service website; each service was presented in an A5 size card with 4 related pictures and descriptions of service feature. Participants were asked to express their views of these services.

We linked the interview data to statements and use an affinity diagram to analyze the data. Affinity diagrams are used to categorize the values of various roles. In the case sharing part, as shown in Figure 1, we used ladder interviews to construct mean-ends chains. This technique is used to find unconscious motives and the values behind them. It can help researchers to meaningfully connect product attributes with consumer's values (Gutman, 1988).

CULTURAL PROBE

After obtaining the preference of the users, we found that when people face death, they are concerned about sharing their precious memories with their loved ones more than preserving their lives. In order to obtain more information about the interactions between users and their loved ones, we used cultural probes to understand their lives, including the people they cared about, the important things they preserved, the situation of the final moment they want and the personality they want to preserve. For the sake of making users comfortable and relieved when doing the workbook, we used a scenario of taking a train to outer space and never coming back, instead of facing death. There are 7 days in this workbook; during the first 6 days, we asked users to imagine if they are going to leave, what would they leave behind? On the last day, we asked the participants to imagine if they had already left their love ones, what messages they will send to their love ones via our service.

Ten people aged 30-65 participated, 6 men and 4 women; in order to collect the things in their lives, we asked the participants to take photos of the objects they wanted to give to their loved ones and the things that can represent them. In order to understand their preferences for using technology to enrich the content of the relic, we also asked the participants to choose the technology they might use.

We collated the data of the workbooks into flow models, with the object they chose and their motivations.

RESULTS AND FINDING

Our findings are related to three aspects. Firstly, we discussed the connection between the users and their loved ones in order to clarify the reasons behind their choices. Secondly, we reorganized the objects they chose to determine which items were meaningful. Thirdly, during the process their prepared the relic, we listed the difficulties in the preparation process of this relic.

CONNECTIONS

In our study, we found that what users were most concerned about was not preserving themselves perfectly, but determining how to build a new link with their love one through the items they left. As shown in Figure 1, the consolidated flow model presents various roles and their expectation regarding their communication. According to different subjects, people left different objects and contents. For intimate friends or family, they shared memories and expressed thankfulness, concerns, blessing or regrets to strengthen the links between each other. On the other hand, they left a brief self-introduction with personal values in order to have a positive impact for the future generations.

They want to share memories with intimate people

When their loved ones received the relic, people hoped that their loved ones would be happy and savor their 'reruns': *"I will give the relic to intimate friends who will miss me; I want to give them something to match their preferences and I think this relic represents the friendship between us."*

They care about people who are close to them, with whom they got along. They want to leave happy memories in the minds of others, such as group photos with precious memories instead of individual photos.

They want to preserve their life experiences for different people

There is a difference between preserving their life experience for their family and leaving themselves in a public space. They preserve their life for the

Figure 1. The consolidated flow model.

future generations to know their appearance, work and life. They also want to pass down their values and attitudes to life to their children: *"I was a businessman starting from scratch; I want to use biographical record of these processes to make my children treasure what they have."*

They do not really care about other people in the world, they do not think other people will review their life seriously; they just want to examine their experiences, pass down their values and attitudes to life and share their habits or preferences to show their personal impressions. With a brief description of who they are, to prove that they had existed in this world.

OBJECTS

We collected 26 objects that people wanted to give their loved ones and 25 objects that can represent themselves from the workbooks and analyzed the data into flow models, the flow model presents various roles and the objects between the user and loved ones; it also presents the reasons they chose the object.

The relic is a connection between users and their loved ones; there are two ways to build this link.

Firstly, they chose objects that had special meaning both to themselves and their loved ones; these items represent proof of their relationship, a symbol of love for each other. Secondly, they chose the objects with their personal images, including their appearance, habits, life experiences or some souvenirs. These items have distinctive personal characteristics, and can take the place of them to stay in the world. They also care about if this relic could be preserved for a long time; in addition, they also do not want to burden their loved ones because of this relic.

Objects they want to give

34% of objects selected to give their loved ones in our workbooks were articles related to their habits, or which they used to interact with their loved ones, or the objects with special memories; their habits represented who they are, and the objects they used to interact with their loved ones represented their connection and they wished to survive in their loved ones' hearts through these items. 23% of objects selected were the relics they received from their loved ones; they preserved the relic for a long time and hoped that their loved ones could take back the relic and preserve it. Most of the objects that

Image 1: "It is a gift from my friend; I want him to preserve the gift just like my company."

Image 2: This is a piggy bank. I usually saved 50 dollar coins and the kids would dig for the money from the slot; it is a very special experience for

parents gave to their children are things that they were concerned about and hoped to remind their children.

Objects that represent themselves

56% of objects selected to represent themselves were the functional articles for daily use, such as perfume, shoes, bags, glasses. These things are not very special, but things they were accustomed to using, and part of their personal identities. 12% of

Image 3: "I used perfume every day since I was twelve years old."

Image 4: "Hand-made bracelet from a friend, it was worn for a long time."

the objects were accessories with special meaning they wore every day, such as a necklace when s/he was converted to Buddhism and wedding rings. 12% of the objects were related to their habits.

Location for preserving the relic

Due to the fact that modern life is fast-paced and busy all the time, people do not believe that this

Image 5: "The display windows used to collect souvenirs"

Image 6: "A shoe box to keep the relics "

relic will be used frequently. They do not want their loved ones to be immersed in a sad mood; if the relic is placed on public display, they want it to be a happy topic. If this thing is more monumental and filled with memories, they hope the relic could be easily stored until their loved ones need it.

Valuable objects

People like to leave something special behind which is not easy to buy, or which has financial value. They

Image 7: "My collection since I was 30 years old"

Image 8: "I saved these gold necklaces more than 50 years; they have great historical value. I want to give them to my daughters."

believe that the actual use of these things makes it relatively easy to be properly preserved. When their children were facing financial difficulties, the relic can also help their children.

DIFFICULTIES

During the preparation, conduct and completion of the process, they encountered different kinds of difficulties. We used a sequence model to explain their actions and problems, as shown in Figure 2; the sequence model explains a sequence of their intent and actions. There were 3 stages in preparing this relic. Firstly, when they were sick or someone passed away around them and they started to think about this problem and decided what to leave. Secondly, they collated their memories and the things in their daily life, but they did not organize their collections. At the last stage, when they realized they were running out of time, they started to prepare the relic in a short time.

Lack of triggers for making the relic

They were always thinking about leaving something, but never started: "Although I want to leave something for them, it was never done because my life is too busy." They also told their children what they wanted, but the children did not want to face it.

They planned to record their own voice or songs, or write a series of letters for their children. They planned a lot but did not find the right time to do it.

They do not know how to organize their memories
As media technology advances in terms of storage, it is easier for people to store a variety of voice, pictures and videos. They used to collect lots of photos of their life. They want to use these data for the relic but it is not easy for them to organize a huge number of photos.

They hope their loved ones can recover from grief
They wanted to prepare an impressive relic, but they also worried about their loved ones; they were not sure if the relic could relieve the grief or extend the sadness.

They hope to stay in the hearts of their loved ones, accompany their loved ones in hard times, and also believe that as time goes by, people will forget about them. They do not need people to think of them every day: *"If my child really misses me, he will have his own way to miss me, because we had been together and had a wonderful time."*

Intents : Show considerations for relatives and friends
Relief the grief
Say goodbye

Trigger: When they are sick or dying

Figure 2. The consolidated sequence model.

DESIGN SUGGESTIONS

In this study, we clarified users' needs if they were going to prepare the last gift. After analysis of these data, we propose a few design suggestions for

designers when they design memorial products or services.

Integrate the preparations into their lives

Users collected photos to record their lives and also collected souvenirs to record their trip. At the final moment, they want to review these memories with their loved ones but t encountered difficulty when organizing their memories. We propose that the service could help them to organize the photos and also back up their photos in their daily lives,When they upload the photos, they could also attach their feelings or voice and label the friends or family members. When they are going to prepare the relic, they can easily reorganize their memories for different people.

Easily create a desired atmosphere

Users want to present their memories in a lively manner, and can make people feel warm or happy rather than sad. They also hope to merge their personality into this relic, such as their habits, lifestyle, or the music they like. They want to prepare a unique atmosphere with personal identities, and hope that their loved ones will have a good time at the final moment.

Provide different modes of information presentation

People still care about their privacy even after they die; they only want show brief information to people they do not know. They just want to share their lives with their intimate friends or relatives. We propose that services or products provide different data filtering methods, even for their close friends and relatives, so that they could share different memories.

Convenient for storage

People care about if the relic could be properly preserved; they also do not want to trouble their loved ones. They hope the relic could be preserved easily; if the relic is placed as a showpiece in their house, it should not be reminiscent of death, but of happy times.

Combine with the souvenir

People have different souvenirs in their life; most of these objects are related to their loved ones and could be regarded as a connection between them. If the product or service could be combined with the souvenirs, it could be more commemorative for both the users and their loved ones.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we realized what people want to leave when they face death. In further research, we will consider if there are similarities when people change to different stages of their lives, such as graduation or marriage, to determine what people will prepare when they face these situations.

REFERENCES

- Michael, M., Ronald, M.(2010). A Death in the Family : Opportunities for Designing Technologies for the Bereaved. *Proceedings of CHI 2010: Death and Fear*. Atlanta, Georgia, USA. : ACM.
- Hallam, E., Hockey, J.(2001) *Death, Memory, and Material Culture*. Berg, New York, NY, USA.
- Matthew, L., Melissa E., Markaridian, S.(2008) Telepresence after Death. *Journal of Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, Vol. 17, No. 3, 310-325.
- Yuko M., Akihito H., Eiko K., Takeo N.(2006) Psychological process from hospitalization to death among uninformed terminal liver cancer patients in Japan. *Journal of BMC Palliative Care*. Vol. 5, No. 1, 1-10.
- Dennis K., Phyllis R., Steven L.(1996) *Continuing bonds: new understandings of grief*. USA: TAYLOR&FRANCIS.
- Carol R. Ember, Melvin Ember (2004) *Encyclopedia of medical anthropology*. New York : Kluwer Academic/Plenum
- Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1981) *The meaning of things*. USA : Press Syndicate of the University of Cambridge
- Kyriaki, M., Eleni, T., Efi, P., Emmanuela, K., Pavlos, S., Costas, S.(2005) Life before death: identifying preparatory grief through the development of a new measurement in advanced cancer patients (PGAC). *Support Care Cancer*. Vol. 13, 834-841